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A STUDY ON PREVALENCE AND DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN IN DEPARTMENT OF ONCOLOGY OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Background A drug utilization study is intended to describe-quantitatively and qualitatively- the population of users of a given drug and/or the conditions of used in Oncology department, it is a branch of medicine. That deals with the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of cancer. Cancer is not a single disease; rather, it is a group of diseases characterized by uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells. The main aim of the study to improving patient's knowledge on all aspects will boost up the present health care. The objectives of the study to Analyze patterns of drug use among cancer patients. Methodology It is a hospital based prospective observational study. Results Total no. of prescription was 100, in that age group of cancer patients. Alkylating agents (46) are most common prescribed drugs, breast cancer (14%) have high prevalence index, gastro intestinal tract system have high no of carcinoma cases (21%). The most frequently prescribed anticancer drugs were observed to be Alkylating agents 46(31.5%). Among a total of 272adjuvant drugs Dexamethasone (17.72%) and Ondansetron (16.87%) were observed to be majorly prescribed Adjuvant drugs. Major formulations of anti cancer drugs are parenteral (92.46%). applying of WHO drug use indicators for these Study. Conclusion According to WHO drug utilization studies are required for rational use of drug in every clinical practice. The study provides an overview about utilization of anticancer drugs among the patients in hospital and could serve as a basis for further research towards the rational clinical practice, preventive care for cancer and improving patient's knowledge on anticancer drugs on all aspects will boost up the present health care in this settings.

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INTRODUCTION

Drug utilization analysis was outlined by WHO, as the promoting, distribution, prescription and use of medication during a society, with special stress on the ensuing medical, social and economics. Since then, a number of different terms have get use and it is important to know the interrelationships of the various domains.^[1, 2] DUR programs play a vital role in manage the health care systems, interpret, and improve the prescribing, administration, and use of medications and, current review of health care supplier prescribing, dispensing, and patient use of drugs^[3-5]. DUR programs as quality assurance measure provide corrective action; prescriber feedback and further evaluations are made for more efficient use of scarce health care resources^[6, 7]. In this study, objective was to evaluate the cancer prevalence and prescribing pattern of cytotoxic medicines in one of the major tertiary care hospital for cancer treatment and improving patient's knowledge on all aspects will improve the present health care and to Analyze patterns of drug utilization among cancer patients. Chemotherapy is main stay of treatment with other modalities in the management^[8]. A retrospective cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted^[9], as cancer has become an important agenda in the health sector of every country.^[10] Cancer is not a single disease; rather, it is a group of diseases characterized by uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells. Simply, cancer means the change in the body's cells that cause them to grow out of control^[11] Factors that can increase an individual's risk for developing a cancer include environmental and lifestyle factors, genetic predisposition, immunosuppression, and exposure to one or more potential carcinogens^[12]. Appropriate use of drugs is an essential element in achieving quality of health and medical care for patients and the community as a whole^[13]. The irrational use of medicines is a serious problem worldwide. It can result in adverse drug reactions, increased morbidity and mortality rates, wasted resources and higher out-of-pocket costs to patients^[14], which can be minimised by pharmacist who is expert in the area of medication therapy management^[15-17]. The ultimate goal in cancer chemotherapy is to use advances in cell biology to develop drugs that selectively target specific cancer cells. Chemotherapy drugs are powerful medicines that can cause many side effects.^[18,19] According to health ministry data, out of more than 300 cancer centres in India, 40 percent are not adequately equipped with advanced cancer care equipment. Currently in India will need at least 600 additional cancer care centres by 2020 to meet the requirements as per standard reports.^[20] Cancer chemotherapy remains an intriguing area of pharmacology. On the one hand, use of anticancer drugs produces high rates of cure of diseases, which, without chemotherapy, result in extremely high mortality rates. The anticancer drugs are more toxic than any other pharmaceuticals agents, and thus their benefit must be carefully weighed against their risks. Many of the available drugs are cytotoxic agents that act on all dividing cells, cancerous or normal.

METHODOLOGY

It was a hospital based retrospective drug utilization study, conducted after getting Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) approval and with permission of Medical Superintendent. The study period is 3 months (January 2017 to march 2017) carried in multispecialty hospital in Andhra Pradesh

Inclusion criteria

1. In patients who are diagnosed with cancer
2. In patients with cancer in the all age group

Exclusion criteria

1. Patients who are admitted to the ICU
2. Patients who are pregnancy and lactating.
3. Patients who are admitted for radiation therapy

Study Procedure

Data Collection: Daily regular ward rounds were carried out in the study site during the study period along with the junior and senior physicians. The data were collected and recorded in a specially designed data entry format. Prior to data collection, written consent from the patient/bystander was obtained on a patient consent form. Data Analysis: The obtained data during the ward rounds were thoroughly analysed to evaluate inappropriateness in drug using. Assessment of prescription patterns as per the WHO drug use indicators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Age and Gender Distribution

Table 1 illustrates the age gender distribution of cancer patients.

S. No	Age	Male	Female	Total Patients	Percentage (%)
1	0-10	3	1	4	4%
2	11-20	10	1	11	11%
3	21-30	1	1	2	2%
4	31-40	3	3	6	6%
5	41-50	12	13	25	25%
6	51-60	7	18	25	25%
7	>60	16	11	27	27%

Figure 1 illustrates the age gender distribution of cancer patients.

Among sample size of 100 patients, the age group with high incidence of cancer was found to be people >60years (27%) out of it were males. And low incidence of cancer was found to be between age group 21-30 (2%).the frequency of cancer was found to be more in females between age group 51-60 and more in males between age group >60years.

II. Physiological System wise Distributions of Cancer

Table 2 illustrates physiological system wise distribution of different types of cancer.

S. No	Physiological System	Number Of patients
1	Oral Cavity	4
2	Gastro Intestinal Tract	21
3	Genito Urinary Tract	19
4	Respiratory Tract	6
5	Other Carcinomas	50

Figure 2 illustrates physiological system wise distribution of different types of cancer.

The physiological system wise distribution of different types of cancer. Out of sample size of 100 cases other types of cancers like Breast cancers, lymphomas, and leukaemia were found with higher incidence (50%) and carcinomas of oral cavity were observed to be with lower incidence (4%).

III. Distribution of Types of Cancer

Table 3 illustrates the Types of cancer.

S. No	Type of Cancer	Number Of Patients
1	B Cell Acute Lymphocytic Leukemia	9
2	T Cell Acute Lymphocytic Leukemia	2
3	Chronic Myeloblastic Leukemia	3
4	Carcinoma Breast	14
5	Carcinoma Vagina	2
6	Carcinoma Cervix	8
7	Carcinoma Colon	7
8	Bilateral Retinoblastoma	1
9	Carcinoma Tongue	2
10	Non Hodgkin Lymphoma	3
11	Hodgkins Lymphoma	2
12	Multiple Myeloma	4
13	Carcinoma Anal Canal	1
14	Small Cell Lung Carcinoma	1
15	Non Small Cell Lung Carcinoma	5
16	Carcinoma Pancreas	2
17	Carcinoma Oesophagus	2
18	Thalamic Basal Ganglia Tumor	1
19	Carcinoma Pyriform Fossa	2
20	Carcinoma Post Cricoid With Neck Node	1
21	Acute Myeloid Leukemia	4
22	Primitive Neuroectodermal Tumour	1
23	Epithelial Ovarian Carcinoma	5
24	Teratocarcinoma Ovary	1
25	Periapillary Carcinoma	2
26	Carcinoma Stomach	5
27	Acute Promyelocytic Leucaemia	2
28	Pseudomyxoma Peritoneum-Appendix	3
29	Carcinoma Prostate	2
30	Carcinoma Endometrium	1
31	Transitional Cell Carcinoma	1
32	Carcinoma Intestine	1

Figure 3 illustrates the Types of cancer.

Table 3 illustrates the Types of cancer. A total of 32 types of cancer were observed during the study period. Among the total number of 100 cases collected, Carcinoma Breast cases were found with higher incidence (14%), next to acute lymphocytic leukaemia (9%). The incidence of cancers like Bilateral retinoblastoma, Small cell lung carcinoma, carcinoma anal canal, Teratocarcinoma ovary, carcinoma intestine, endometrial carcinomas were found with lower incidence (1%).

IV. Prescribing Patterns of Anti-cancer Drugs

Table 4 illustrates the prescribing pattern of anti cancer drugs.

S.No	Type	Group	Name Of The Drug	Number Of Cases
01	Alkylating agents	Nitrogen mustards	Cyclophosphamide	5
			Ifosfamide	1
			bendamustin	1
		Platinum compounds	Cisplatin	9
			Carboplatin	17
			oxaliplatin	12
			dacarbazine	1
02	Antimetabolites	Folate antagonists	Methotrexate	8
			pemetrexed	2
		Pyrimidine pahway	Capecitabine	9
			Decitabine	2
			Fluorouracil	11
			Gemcitabine	6
			Cytarabine	2
03	Cytotoxic antibiotics	Purine pathway	mercaptopurine	4
		Anthracyclines	Daunorubicin	2
			Doxorubicin	1
			Epirubicin	1
		Other	Bleomycin	1
		Adriamycin	5	
		04	Plant derivatives and similar compounds	Taxanes
Paclitaxel	6			
Vinca alkaloids	Vincristine			6
	Vinblastin			1
	Other			Etoposide
Camptothecins	Irinotecan			5
05	Protein kinase inhibitors			Tyrosine or other kinase inhibitors
		Dasatinib	1	
06	Monoclonal antibodies	Anti EGF,EGF-2	Trastuzumab	7
			Panitumumab	1
		Anti CD20/CD30/CD52	Rituximab	3
		Anti VEGF	Bevacizumab	3
07	Miscellaneous	Proteasome inhibitor	Bortezomib	3
08	Hormone antagonists	Androgen receptor antagonist	Abiraterone	1
			Bicalutamide	1

Figure 4 illustrates the prescribing pattern of categories of anti cancer drugs.

Table 4 illustrates the prescribing pattern of anti cancer drugs. The most frequently prescribed anticancer drugs were observed to be Alkylating agents and the Protein kinase inhibitors were used less frequently.

V. Different type of adjuvant drugs

Table 5 illustrates the different types of adjuvant drugs prescribed.

S.no	Name of the drugs	No of prescriptions
01	Ondansetron	40
02	Dexamethasone	42
03	Hydrocortisone	10
04	Pheneramine maleate	11
05	Ranitidine	9
06	Pantocid	21
07	Syp.Broncorex	8
08	Cap.Zincovit	12
09	Syp.Looz	12
10	Metrogyl	6
11	syp.Citralka	5
12	Inj.Imipinem+Cilastatin	2
13	Syp.Duphalac	15
14	T.B complex	7
15	Lorazepam	3
16	Mesna	2
17	Paracetamol	6
18	Shelcal	3
19	Ultracet	11
20	Acetazolamide	4
21	Pregabalin	1
22	Prednisolone	3
23	Piperacillin+Tazobactam	1
24	Cefoperazone	3
25	Levofloxacin	5
26	Amoxicillin+clavulanic	4
27	acid	2
28	Fluconazole	4
29	Domperidone	11
30	Leucoverin PEG Filgrastim	9

Among a total of 272 adjuvant drugs Dexamethasone (17.72%) and Ondansetron (16.87%) were observed to be majorly prescribed Adjuvant drugs and Pregabalin (0.42%) was less frequently prescribed.

VI. Different Type of Anti Cancer Drug Formulations

Table 6 illustrates the parenteral route and oral formulations of anticancer drugs.

S.no	Type of formulation	No of drugs	Percentage (%)
01	Parenteral	134	92.46
02	Oral	12	7.53

Figure 5 illustrates the different formulation types of anticancer drugs.

Out of total 146 anticancer drugs 134 drugs were observed as parenteral route which accounts for 92.46 % and 12 drugs were tablets accounting 7.53%.

VII. Cytoprotectant Drugs

Table 7 illustrates the list of cytoprotectant drugs.

S.no	Drug	Male	Female	Total
1	Peg Filgrastim	4	5	9
2	Leucovorin	6	5	11
3	Mesna	2	0	2

Table 7 illustrates the list of cytoprotectant drugs prescribed in the sample size of 100 cancer cases taken. Among the three types of cytoprotectant drugs leucovorin was found to be majorly prescribed and means was observed to be prescribed with less frequency.

VIII. Distribution of WHO drug use indicators

Table 8 illustrates the Distribution of WHO drug use indicators.

S. No	WHO Prescribing indicators	Frequency
01	Number of drugs per prescription	
	One	11
	Two	26
	Three	17
	Four	16
	more than four	30
	Average number of drug per prescription	
02	Number of drug prescribed by generic name	4.18
03	Number of drug prescribed by brand name	183
04	Number of antibiotics were prescribed	235
05	Number of drug prescribed from EDL	27
06	Number of geriatric prescriptions	340
07		50

Table 8 illustrates the distribution of WHO drug use indicators. The present study shows that average number of drugs per prescription was 4.18. This is because the anticancer patients are to be treated with other drugs like Antiemetics, Proton pump inhibitors, vitamin supplements etc in addition to cytotoxic drugs. This study supports the results of previous study carried out in Nepal^[9]. Out of a total of 418 numbers of drugs 81.33% of drugs prescribed were found to be from EDL.

DISCUSSION

A survey based on the prescription is considered to be one of the most cost-effective methods to determine the prescribing approach of physicians^[1]. The objective of our study was to evaluate the drug prescription patterns and prevalence of cancer among patients admitted to the cancer hospital of a tertiary care hospital. The prevalence of cancer was found to be high in age group of >60 years(27%),and low between age group of 21-30years(2%).among which females are more prone to cancer in age group between 51-60 years and males of age>60years.In the present study 32 types of cancer were observed during the study period, which revealed that carcinoma breast cases were found with higher incidence (14%) and other types of cancers like Bilateral retinoblastoma ,Small cell lung carcinoma, carcinoma anal canal, Teratocarcinoma ovary, carcinoma intestine, endometrial carcinomas were found with lower incidence (1%). Incidence of breast cancer in India is on rise and is the second most cause of death in females in southern India.^[2] The most frequently prescribed anticancer drugs were observed to be Alkylating agents and the Protein kinase inhibitors were used less frequently. One of the study also revealed that Alkylating agents constituted the major portion with drugs acting on hormonal milieus constituting the least.^[3]A total number of 146 anti-cancer drugs were found & the formulation mostly prescribed was parenteral having 92.46% and oral formulations were less frequently prescribed 7.53%.Cytoprotectant drugs were also prescribed along with anticancer drugs out of which leucovorin was found to be majorly prescribed and mesna was observed to be prescribed with less frequency.

CONCLUSION

The study provides an overview about utilization of anticancer drugs among our study patients in our hospital and could serve as a basis for further research, our result implies that there is an increased drug use of anticancer drugs in our study period indicates the necessity of preventive care for cancer and improving patient's knowledge on anticancer drugs on all aspects will boost up the present health care in this settings.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors are not having any conflicts of interest to declare

ABBRIATIONS

WHO	:	World health organization
DUS	:	Drug Utilization study
ALL	:	Acute lymphoid leukaemia
EDL	:	Essential Drug list
PEG	:	Poly ethylene glycol
AML	:	Acute Myeloid Leukemia
IEC	:	Institutional Ethics Committee
ICU	:	Intensive care unit

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